

TECHNISCHE
UNIVERSITÄT
WIEN

Data management plan (DMP)

Wind Power Capacity Municipality Denmark

[acronym]

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	22/11/2024	First version of the DMP – created for the start of the project

Level of distribution		This DMP is licensed under a <u>Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)</u> . It is publicly available under https://orcid.org/0009-0006-0409-080X .
-----------------------	---	--

Project details

Project Coordinator Principal Investigator	
Contact person (responsible for data management and DMP)	Anton Pehrsson, e12405427@student.tuwien.ac.at, ORCID iD: 0009-0006-0409-080X
Contributors	Anton Pehrsson, e12405427@student.tuwien.ac.at, ORCID iD: 0009-0006-0409-080X, Data Manager
Start date	2024-11-20
End date	2024-12-04
Funder, funding programme, grant number	
Internal project number TU Wien	

List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
...	...
...	...
...	...
...	...
...	...
...	...

Content

INTRODUCTION	4
Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data	4
Relevant Policies and Guidelines	4
1. DATA DESCRIPTION	5
1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced	5
1b Data generation and reuse	5
2. DOCUMENTATION AND DATA QUALITY	5
2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation	5
2b Data quality control	6
3. STORAGE AND BACKUP DURING RESEARCH PROCESS	6
3a Storage and backup facilities	6
3b Data security and protection of sensitive data	6
4. LEGAL AND ETHICAL REQUIREMENTS	6
4a Personal data	6
4b Intellectual property rights and ownership	6
4c Ethical issues	7
5. DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION	7
5a Data publication and access conditions	7
5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data	7
6. RDM RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES	7
6a RDM-roles and responsibilities	7
6b Resources	7

Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20%E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Results	Standard office documents	xlsx	100 MB	no

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Capacity per Municipality	https://www.energidataservice.dk/tso-electricity/CapacityPerMunicipality#metadata-info	CC BY 4.0	no
R2	Production per Municipality per Hour	https://www.energidataservice.dk/tso-electricity/ProductionMunicipalityHour	CC BY 4.0	no

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

After downloading the datasets, the data will be analyzed and filtered according to the municipality's id-number. The information of the municipality-IDs are gathered from info.stat.dk. The analysis will be done through inserting the downloaded csv-files to Microsoft Excel in order to compile a comparison between each municipality's ratio of wind power source and number of wind turbines. The comparison will result in a newly created graf that more easily displays which municipalities produce and have the most capacity of wind power, both on- and offshore.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The files of datasets will be stored in local maps on the data managers hardrive and the filenames will follow the projects naming convention defined as DatasetTitle_date_version.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used [at file level/at dataset level/at project level]. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

A far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

Documentation of how to access, understand and reuse the data will be provided through a README file. Here will also the data sources and analysis technique be explained in order for future reuse of the data.

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: peer review of data.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU.it. The infrastructure of TU Wien will be used for this purpose.

R1 (Capacity per Municipality), R2 (Production per Municipality per Hour) will be stored on TUownCloud: TUownCloud is a sync&share service provided by TU.it for TU Wien members. It runs on TU.it servers and offers features known from public cloud systems such as Dropbox, for example, the exchange of data with authorized persons. Deleted files can be recovered within 180 days.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	no access
R1	writing	reading only	no access
R2	writing	reading only	no access

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2024-12-04	zenodo		CC-BY-4.0

Methods or software needed to access and use data: No specific tools or software are needed to access the data. When reusing the data, an access to a .xlsx formatted filemanager is needed.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	zenodo	10 years	Students and general public

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The [PI / data officer XY] will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
-----------	-----------	-------------	------	-------

Estimated total costs				0

Coverage of costs

...